

Ortho-Amino Phenyl Alkyl/Aryl Alkyl Ketones Part I : On Direct Synthesis of Some *o*-Aminophenyl Alkyl Ketones

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A series of *o*-nitrophenyl alkyl ketones has been prepared by the action of organo cadmium reagents on *o*-nitro benzoyl chloride. Reduction of these nitrocompounds afforded the corresponding amino-ketones which were characterised through their acetyl derivatives and comparing with those prepared by an alternative route, i.e. by the action of alkyl magnesium halides with acetantranil.

O-Amino-benzylketone I, ($R=CH_2C_6H_5$; $R'=NH_2$) (see Chart I) was required in connection with the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds containing nitrogen atoms. One of the obvious routes for such a preparation was the reduction of the corresponding nitro-ketone I ($R=CH_2C_6H_5$; $R'=NO_2$). The literature survey however, indicated that compounds of the type I ($R=CH_2C_6H_5$; $R'=NO_2$) were unknown. The normal method of nitration of the phenyl benzyl ketones cannot be applied due to nitration of both the phenyl nuclei giving rise to isomeric compounds. In order to have an alternative method of synthesis of such compounds we thought of preparing them by the reaction of organo cadmium compounds on *o*-nitro benzoyl chloride by taking advantage of the fact that organo cadmium compounds do not react with a nitro group in an aromatic nucleus^{1,2}.

The present communication describes successful synthesis of some *o*-nitro phenyl alkyl ketones I(b) and their corresponding amino derivatives I(c). The present method gives *o*-nitro phenyl alkyl ketones (Ib) directly in contrast to several literature methods³⁻¹⁰ wherein nitration^{3,4,5} of phenyl alkyl ketones is adopted and the separation of the resulting isomers is reported to be tedious and clumsy. Only the first three compounds in the series of *o*-nitro phenyl alkyl ketones are known in the literature. Thus it could be seen that there was no

general method known for preparing these compounds. Our method consists of the reaction of cadmium alkyls on *o*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (Ia) according to the method described in the experimental part. The resulting ketones were purified by column chromatography and vacuum distillation and their purity checked by TLC/VPC analysis. They showed UV absorption between 254-257 nm and 215-218 nm and have characteristic bands in the infrared region at 3480-3040 cm^{-1} , 1610-1570 cm^{-1} , 1527-1351 cm^{-1} and 847-649 cm^{-1} . The nitro-ketones were reduced by Tin/HCl to the corresponding amino-ketones in good yields and were characterised by acetyl and 2, 4-DNP derivatives. The N-acetyl derivatives were also prepared by another route using inverse Grignard reaction starting from acetantranil and reacting it with alkylmagnesium-halides. These on hydrolysis afforded *o*-amino phenyl alkyl ketones (Ic). Both the acetyl derivatives as well as the amino compounds prepared by both methods have superimposable IR spectra. Solid acetyl derivatives were checked by mixed m.p. determination also. The reaction sequence is given in Chart I and the properties of the compounds are given in Tables 1, 2, 3.

The reaction of dibenzyl cadmium on *o*-nitrobenzoyl chloride, however, did not give the expected *o*-nitrophenyl-benzyl ketone. Instead we isolated by elaborate chromatography dibenzyl (m.p. 52-53°)^{10a} and benzyl ester of *o*-nitrobenzoic acid (b.p. 160°/7 mm).

Experimental

All m.p.s. and b.ps. are uncorrected. The IR spectra were taken in Nujol for solids or as liquid

TABLE-1 PROPERTIES OF ORTHO-NITRO PHENYL ALKYL KETONES AND THEIR DERIVATIVES

S. No.	Ketone Ib	B.P. (B.T.) in °C	Yield %	Elemental Analysis(%)		Derivatives/m.p. in °C
				Found	Calcd.	
1.	R=CH ₃	145/150°/4-6 mm	44.26	C 57.98 H 4.23 N 8.19	58.18 4.27 8.48	1) Semicarbazone 209-210° (lit.m.p. 208-210°) ⁹ 2) 2 : 4 DNP. 174° (lit. m.p.168-70°) ⁹ .
2.	R=C ₂ H ₅	160-165°/5-6 mm	40.57	C 60.37 H 5.26 N 7.39	60.33 5.16 7.82	1) Semicarbazone 181-182° (lit. m.p. 180-181°) ¹⁰ 2) 2 : 4 DNP. 149°-150°
	R=C ₃ H ₇ (n)	165-170°/5-6 mm	34.64	C 62.36 H 5.64 N 7.00	62.15 5.74 7.25	2 : 4 DNP. 162-163°
4.	R=C ₄ H ₉ (n)	165-170°/5-6 mm	34.41	C 63.69 H 6.37 N 7.04	63.75 6.32 6.96	2 : 4 DNP. 204-205°
5.	R=C ₅ H ₁₁ (n)	150-155°/4-5 mm	31.52	C 65.31 H 6.59 N 6.61	65.14 6.83 6.33	2 : 4 DNP. 158-159°
6.	R=C ₆ H ₁₃ (n)	155-160°/3 mm	28.34	C 66.41 H 7.23 N 5.63	66.36 7.28 5.95	2 : 4 DNP. 200°

TABLE-2 PROPERTIES OF *ortho*-AMINO-PHENYL-ALKYL KETONES.

S. No.	Ketone Ic	B.P. (B.T.) in °C	Yield %	Elemental Analysis(%)		Derivatives M.P./B.P. in °C
				Found	Calcd.	
1.	R=CH ₃	110-15°/7-8 mm	63.5	C 70.98 H 6.93 N 10.03	71.09 6.71 10.36	1) Acetyl der. 73-74° (Lit. m.p. 74-75°) ¹¹ 2) Semicarbazone 289-290 (Lit. m.p. 290°) ¹²
2.	R=C ₂ H ₅	128-130°/4 mm	49.0	C 72.51 H 7.32 N 9.10	72.45 7.43 9.39	1) Acetyl der. 70-71° (Lit. m.p. 70-71°) ¹¹ 2) Semicarbazone 189-190° (Lit. m.p. 189-190°) ¹³
3.	R=C ₃ H ₇ (n)	148-152°/2 mm	63.9	C 73.67 H 8.07 N 8.52	73.49 8.03 8.58	Acetyl der. 42-43°
4.	R=C ₄ H ₉ (n)	148-150°/2 mm	45.8	C 74.61 H 8.67 N 8.13	74.54 8.53 7.90	1) Acetyl der. 154-156°/5 mm. 2) Benzyl der. 72-73°
5.	R=C ₆ H ₁₁ (n)	150-152°/3 mm	47.4	C 75.43 H 8.91 N 7.63	75.35 8.96 7.32	Acetyl der. 175-180°/3 mm
6.	R=C ₆ H ₁₃ (n)	158°/2 mm	38.2	C 75.93 H 9.41 N 7.02	76.05 9.33 6.82	Acetyl der. 200-205°/6 mm

TABLE-3 PROPERTIES OF *ortho*-ACETAMINO PHENYL ALKYL KETONES (BY INVERSE GRIGNARD REACTION)

S. No.	Ketone Id	Yield %	M. P./B. P. (B. T.) in °C	Elemental analysis (%)	
				Found/	Calcd.
1.	R=CH ₃	32.38	73-74° (Lit. m.p. 74-75°) ¹¹	C 67.59 H 6.27 N 7.95	67.78 6.26 7.91
2.	R=C ₂ H ₅	34.53	70-71° (Lit. m.p. 70-71°) ¹¹	C 69.23 H 6.79 N 7.40	69.09 6.85 7.33
3.	R=C ₃ H ₇ (n)	43.11	45-46°	C 70.15 H 7.12 N 6.92	70.22 7.37 6.82
4.	R=C ₄ H ₉ (n)	48.62	154-160°/3-4 mm	C 71.31 H 7.80 N 6.48	71.20 7.82 6.39
5.	R=C ₆ H ₁₁ (n)	36.76	170-174°/3 mm	C 71.88 H 8.32 N 6.30	72.02 8.21 6.00
6.	R=C ₆ H ₁₃ (n)	34.88	190-195°/2-3 mm	C 72.63 H 8.50 N 5.72	72.84 8.56 5.66

films in the case of liquids. UV spectra were taken in ethanol (spec.).

(a) *General method of preparing o-nitrophenyl alkyl ketones (1b)*. In a 500 ml round bottomed flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer, a reflux condenser with a calcium chloride guard-tube and a dropping funnel, were taken 2 gms of magnesium turnings activated by iodine and 50 ml of dried ether. To this, 0.08 mol. of alkyl halide (bromide or iodide) was added in portions and the reaction was allowed to take place in cold. When most of the magnesium was dissolved, it was heated on a water-bath for half an hour to complete the Grignard reaction. It was then cooled and 6 gms of freshly dried cadmium chloride was added in one lot and refluxed again for half an hour or until it showed a negative test to the Gilman's reagent¹⁴.

The above solution was cooled to room temperature and a benzene solution of *o*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (prepared according to literature method)¹⁵ was added in small portions with cooling. After the complete addition of the acid chloride, the white mixture was refluxed on water bath for 3 hrs. It was then decomposed by hydrochloric acid and ice. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted twice with benzene. The benzene layer and the extracts were combined, washed with water, 10% Na₂CO₃ solution and again with water. Finally it was washed with a saturated solution of sodium thiosulphate. The benzene layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and given charcoal treatment. Benzene was removed and the residue passed over alumina Gr. II (1 : 30). It was eluted successively with pet. ether, pet. ether-benzene mixture, benzene and finally with ether. The benzene eluate afforded the desired ketone. It was tested by VPC/TLC and shown to be a single compound. It was concentrated and distilled under reduced pressure to get a clean product and was characterized by preparing a suitable derivative and other spectral studies (Table 1).

(b) *Reduction of ortho-nitro phenyl alkyl ketones by tin and hydrochloric acid method. Preparation of o-aminophenyl alkyl ketones (1c) General procedure*: The reduction was carried out by following the general procedure mentioned in the "Text-book of Practical Organic Chemistry" by Vogel; p. 563, 3rd edition (1956), Longman Green and Co-Ltd., London W1. The amino ketone was isolated in pure form by steam distillation followed by distillation under reduced pressure. It was characterized by preparing a suitable derivative and other spectral studies (Table 2).

(c) *General procedure for preparing ortho-acetamino phenyl alkyl ketones by inverse Grignard method (1d)*: Acetantranil (2 methyl, 3:1:4 benzoxazone) prepared according to the method of Bogert *et al*¹⁶ was used for this reaction.

1.5 gms of Magnesium turnings were taken in a 3 necked round bottomed flask fitted with a mercury sealed mechanical stirrer, dropping funnel with a guard-tube and a reflux condenser with a guard-tube. The system was flushed with nitrogen to begin with and further reaction was carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen. 50 ml of dry ether was added. To this was added 0.06 mole of alkyl halide. When almost all magnesium was dissolved, it was refluxed for half an hour to complete the Grignard reaction.

10 gms of acetantranil were dissolved in 125 ml of dry benzene, in a three necked flask fitted with a mercury sealed stirrer, dropping funnel and a reflux condenser with a CaCl₂ guard-tube. The above Grignard solution from the first three-necked flask was forced by nitrogen into the dropping funnel of the second flask (by means of mechanical stirring) and the addition made dropwise, with stirring at 0° during addition. When the addition was over the flask was heated for an hour with an infrared lamp and then cooled.

To this cooled solution was added dropwise conc. hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) till acidic. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with benzene once and twice with ether. The benzene and the ether extracts were mixed and washed free of acid by water and 10% sodium carbonate solution and finally again with water. After removing the solvent, the product was crystallized from dil. alcohol if it was solid or vacuum distilled if it was liquid. Thus a pure *ortho*-acetamino phenyl alkyl ketone was obtained.

Conversion of o-acetamido phenyl alkyl ketone (1d) to o-amino phenyl alkyl ketone (1c): To get the free amino from the acetamido ketone, it was refluxed over conc. hydrochloric acid-alcohol for 2 hrs., cooled and made alkaline with liquor ammonia, diluted and extracted with ether. After removal of ether, the compound was crystallised in alcohol if it was solid or vacuum distilled, if liquid.

Attempted preparation of ortho-nitro phenyl benzyl ketone (R=CH₂C₆H₅), R=NO₂

The reaction of dibenzyl cadmium on *o*-nitrobenzoyl chloride was carried out following the general method described above. The reaction product was worked up as usual and purified by vacuum distillation and chromatography over alumina Gr. II (1 : 30), using P. E., benzene and ether as eluents. The product in P. E. fraction was solid and characterized as dibenzyl (m. p. 52°).

Analysis: Found: C, 91.86; H, 7.74 per cent calculated for C₁₄H₁₄, C, 92.26; H, 7.74 per cent.

Benzene ether fractions collected in the above chromatography over alumina Gr. II, were found to

be impure by TLC ; they were mixed together and rechromatographed over silica-gel (1 : 25) using P. C., benzene and ether as eluents. Benzene fraction contained a pleasant smelling compound identified as benzyl ortho-nitrobenzoate as a yellow coloured liquid B. P. 160°/7 mm.

Analysis : Found : C, 65.51 ; H, 4.39 ; N, 5.83 per cent.

Calculated for $C_{14}H_{11}NO_4$ C, 65.36 ; H, 4.31 ; N, 5.49 per cent.

Molecular wt. as determined from mass spectral analysis, was found to be 257.

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